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Balancing Economic Growth with Environmental and Healthcare Considerations: Insights from Pakistan's Development Trajectory

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ABSTRACT

Pakistan's economic growth has been a subject of interest, particularly regarding the balance between development, environment, and healthcare. From 1990 to 2020, various factors such as carbon emissions, health infrastructure, high-tech exports, industry value added, and renewable energy consumption have shaped the country's development trajectory. Robust statistical analyses, including least squares regression and Granger causality tests, provide insights into the relationships between these factors and economic growth. The results show a positive association between carbon emissions and economic growth, urging sustainable policies to curb emissions. It also highlights the positive impacts of health infrastructure, industrialization, and renewable energy demand on economic growth. Policymakers should recognize the potential of investing in healthcare and renewable energy for economic prosperity and public welfare. Moreover, technological advancements and high-tech exports contribute to economic expansion. Improving healthcare accessibility can reduce emissions and promote clean energy adoption, benefiting public health and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Economic growth; Carbon emissions; Health infrastructure; Industry value added; Renewable energy demand; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development, driven by the energy transition, is vital for global economies facing increasing growth rates (Chen et al., 2023). The challenge lies in balancing economic expansion with finite energy resources and environmental concerns (Khan & Imran, 2023). Adopting renewable energy sources becomes crucial for achieving sustainable development goals and addressing GHG emissions (Jahanger et al., 2023). Public health programs are essential, especially in developing countries with limited expenditure capacity (Saleem, 2023). The circular economy offers a solution to promote sustainable development, considering economic, societal, and environmental factors (Upadhyay et al., 2023). Transportation and logistics companies contribute significantly to CO₂ emissions, necessitating sustainable practices. Mitigating climate change and fostering green economic growth is crucial in addressing environmental and developmental challenges (Khan, 2023a). Renewable energy sources can improve environmental and economic performance (Nazir, 2023). Prioritizing environmental preservation can positively impact public health expenditures and contribute to economic growth. Strengthening financial stability and implementing social pension schemes are crucial in achieving sustainable development goals (Zaman, 2023a,b).

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This research aims to explore the relationships between economic growth, environmental factors, and public health in Pakistan using robust statistical techniques. It investigated the impact of carbon emissions, health infrastructure, high-technology exports, industry value added, and renewable energy consumption on Pakistan's economic development. The findings provide valuable insights to policymakers, guiding strategies for sustainable economic growth in Pakistan (Zaman, 2023c).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic growth is a crucial objective for countries but must be balanced with environmental sustainability and public health. Raihan & Tuspekova (2022) studied CO₂ emissions in Brazil and found that economic growth, fossil fuel use, urbanization, tourism, and agriculture contributed to environmental degradation, while renewable energy and forests mitigated emissions. Zahoor et al. (2022) examined China's clean energy investment impact, showing it reduced CO₂ emissions but enhanced economic growth. Financial development and urbanization had positive associations with CO₂ emissions and ecological footprint. Gillani et al. (2022) observed that child malnutrition decreased when Pakistan's economy improved. The CPEC project increased women's autonomy in the Thar area, as pointed out by Kumar et al. (2022). The consequences of political instability on Pakistan's clean energy consumption and environmental quality were studied by Sohail et al. (2022). Ali et al. (2023a) examined how public-private energy partnerships affect CO₂ emissions with an eye on renewable energy's future viability. Hieu and Mai (2023) studied the effects of energy consumption on economic development in 80 developing countries and found that both renewable and nonrenewable energy contributed to this effect. Policymakers may employ tax credits and subsidies to promote renewable energy sources and economic development in low-income nations.

The environmental effects of economic development, globalization, and renewable and nonrenewable energy sources in South America from 1995 to 2020 were investigated by Ali et al. (2023b). Results showed that both short- and long-term environmental contamination rose with economic expansion but reduced with greater usage of renewable energy. The long-term effects of economic globalization on pollution, however, were good. From 1990 to 2019, Purnomo et al. (2023) evaluated the impact of several variables on Indonesia's economic development. Consumption of oil, gas, and biomass fuels, as well as average educational attainment, were all determined to benefit economic development. There was no correlation between the quality of roads and life expectancy. Carbon emissions, renewable energy consumption, exports, foreign direct investment, and savings all had a favourable long-run influence on economic development in BRICS nations from 2000 to 2018, according to research by Iqbal et al. (2023). The consequences of interest rates and increased trade openness were unfavourable. The effects of petroleum consumption on carbon emissions in Bangladesh were analyzed by Cheng et al. (2023), who called for less reliance on petroleum and incorporating environmental goals into economic development plans.

Vyas et al. (2023) investigated the link between hazardous air, health expenditure, and GDP growth in India, highlighting the consequences of improving air quality, allocating health funds, and promoting economic development. Munir & Satti's (2023) Solow model analysis showed that foreign assistance was negatively associated with economic growth in Pakistan. In contrast, the size of the labour force was found to have a positive link with growth. Sustainable development and economic growth in Pakistan were examined by Aqib & Zaman (2023). Azam et al. (2023) examined what variables affect life expectancy in Pakistan and found environmental deterioration to be a major contributor, suggesting stricter controls on carbon emissions. The long- and short-term impacts of globalization on Pakistan's GDP were analyzed by Javed et al. (2023). Amir et al. (2023) looked at how Pakistan's economic development was affected by the country's educational system and human resources. The effects of green technology innovation and international tourism on GDP development and GHG emissions in high-income nations were analyzed by Razzaq et al. (2023).

These studies contribute valuable insights into economic growth, energy consumption, environmental sustainability, and policy recommendations for sustainable development in different countries. They employ rigorous econometric methods to analyze time series data and draw important implications for policymakers and stakeholders concerned with environmental preservation, economic progress, and human well-being. Based on the cited literature, the study formed the following research hypotheses, i.e.,

H1: Carbon emissions are likely to increase economic growth on the cost of healthcare damages.

H2: Sustainable healthcare infrastructure will likely increase economic development and high-technology exports.

H3: Sustainable production and green energy sources would likely sustain the country's economic growth.

The study makes several significant contributions. Firstly, it addresses a notable research gap, as only limited studies have examined health performance in a country's efforts to reduce carbon emissions (Campbell-Lendrum et al., 2023; Alandejani & Al-Shaer, 2023). By incorporating this aspect into the growth trajectory analysis, policymakers gain valuable insights to propose sustainable healthcare policies for Pakistan and globally. Secondly, prior research predominantly focused on the industrial sector's contribution to the country's GDP and its impact on development, particularly in rapid urbanization (Aqib & Zaman, 2023; Abbas et al. 2023). *Research Letters*, 1(1), 17-26 (2023)

al., 2023). However, this study goes beyond that and incorporates high-technology exports alongside the country's production, providing a more comprehensive and robust analysis. Such an approach equips policymakers with the necessary information to diversify and expand the country's trade portfolio. Lastly, the study emphasizes the importance of clean and green energy sources, which have received limited attention in previous literature despite their potential for sustainable economic development (Raihan, 2023; Shang et al., 2023). By considering and integrating this aspect into the country's growth trajectory, the study advocates for a sustainable pathway towards economic progress while maintaining low sensitivity to carbon emissions.

These contributions collectively enhance our understanding of the intricate relationship between health performance, carbon emissions reduction efforts, and sustainable economic development. Policymakers can utilize these findings to foster positive changes in Pakistan's development trajectory, paving the way for a more sustainable and resilient future.

3. METHODOLOGY

The econometric framework used in the study involves estimating a multiple linear regression model to investigate the relationship between GDP (economic growth) and the independent variables: CO2 (carbon emissions), HP (health performance), HTE (high technology export), INVA (industry value added), and REC (renewable energy consumption). The model is represented as:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * CO2 + \beta_2 * HP + \beta_3 * HTE + \beta_4 * INVA + \beta_5 * REC + u \tag{1}$$

Where:

- GDP represents economic growth measured by Gross Domestic Product per capita in Pakistan.
- CO2 represents environmental performance measured in metric tons of carbon emissions per capita.
- HP represents health performance measured by the number of physicians available per 1000 people.
- HTE represents high technology export measured as a percentage of manufacturing export goods.
- INVA represents industry value added measured as the annual percentage of growth.
- REC represents renewable energy consumption measured as a percentage of total final energy consumption in the country.

The study employed the Robust Least Squares Regression method to estimate the model coefficients. Robust regression is used when the data may have influential observations or outliers, as it provides better estimates of the regression coefficients under such circumstances. In the empirical literature, Zaman (2023d) presents alternative regression specifications where cross-sectional factors simultaneously influence the response variable of other countries. This particular specification has gained popularity in contemporary research. Additionally, Zaman (2023e) emphasizes the significance of utilizing CiteScore rank to measure academic reputation. Additionally, the study intends to conduct Granger Causality Analysis to determine the causal relationships between the variables. Granger causality analysis helps identify if changes in one variable can predict changes in another, suggesting a potential causal relationship. Equation (2) shows the dynamics of Granger causality in the determinant form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} GDP_t \\ CO2_t \\ HP_t \\ HTE_t \\ INVA_t \\ REC_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_0 \\ \tau_1 \\ \tau_2 \\ \tau_3 \\ \tau_4 \\ \tau_5 \end{bmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^p \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11t} & \sigma_{12t} & \sigma_{13t} & \sigma_{14t} & \sigma_{15t} \\ \sigma_{21t} & \sigma_{22t} & \sigma_{23t} & \sigma_{24t} & \sigma_{25t} \\ \sigma_{31t} & \sigma_{32t} & \sigma_{33t} & \sigma_{34t} & \sigma_{35t} \\ \sigma_{41t} & \sigma_{42t} & \sigma_{43t} & \sigma_{44t} & \sigma_{45t} \\ \sigma_{51t} & \sigma_{52t} & \sigma_{53t} & \sigma_{54t} & \sigma_{55t} \\ \sigma_{61t} & \sigma_{62t} & \sigma_{63t} & \sigma_{64t} & \sigma_{65t} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} GDP_{t-1} \\ CO2_{t-1} \\ HP_{t-1} \\ HTE_{t-1} \\ INVA_{t-1} \\ REC_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \sum_{j=p+1}^{d \max} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{11j} & \theta_{12j} & \theta_{13j} & \theta_{14j} & \theta_{15j} \\ \theta_{21j} & \theta_{22j} & \theta_{23j} & \theta_{24j} & \theta_{25j} \\ \theta_{31j} & \theta_{32j} & \theta_{33j} & \theta_{34j} & \theta_{35j} \\ \theta_{41j} & \theta_{42j} & \theta_{43j} & \theta_{44j} & \theta_{45j} \\ \theta_{51j} & \theta_{52j} & \theta_{53j} & \theta_{54j} & \theta_{55j} \\ \theta_{61j} & \theta_{62j} & \theta_{63j} & \theta_{64j} & \theta_{65j} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} GDP_{t-j} \\ CO2_{t-j} \\ HP_{t-j} \\ HTE_{t-j} \\ INVA_{t-j} \\ REC_{t-j} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_4 \\ \epsilon_5 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

Equations (3 to 8) is simplified by using VAR(2) model of multivariate system, i.e.,

$$GDP_t = C_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_1 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_2 CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_3 HP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_4 HTE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_5 INVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_6 REC_{t-i} + \epsilon \tag{3}$$

$$CO2_t = C_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_1 CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_2 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_3 HP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_4 HTE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_5 INVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_6 REC_{t-i} + \epsilon \tag{4}$$

$$HP_t = C_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_1 HP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_2 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_3 CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_4 HTE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_5 INVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_6 REC_{t-i} + \epsilon \tag{5}$$

$$HTE_t = C_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_1 HTE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_2 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_3 CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_4 HP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_5 INVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_6 REC_{t-i} + \epsilon \tag{6}$$

$$INVA_t = C_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_1 INVA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_2 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_3 CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_4 HP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_5 HTE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_6 REC_{t-i} + \epsilon \tag{7}$$

$$REC_t = C_1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_1 REC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_2 GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_3 CO2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_4 HP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_5 HTE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 \beta_6 INVS_{t-i} + \epsilon \tag{8}$$

4. RESULTS

The study analyzes various factors and their descriptive statistics (see Table 1). Economic growth, measured by GDP per capita, has an average value of 3.303, with a small spread around the mean. GDP per capita distribution is positively skewed, indicating more observations towards higher values. CO2 emissions range from 0.084 to 0.681 metric tons, with a mean of 0.373. The distribution is negatively skewed, concentrating on lower emission levels. High technology export, as a percentage of manufacturing export, has an average value of 0.642, with limited variability around the mean. The distribution is negatively skewed, favouring higher export levels. As a percentage of annual growth, industry value added has an average value of 3.005, with limited variability around the mean. The distribution is approximately symmetrical with slight positive skewness. Renewable energy consumption, as a percentage of total final energy, ranges from 3.7398 to 4.062, with a mean of 3.9062. The variable has a low standard deviation and positively skewed distribution, favoring higher levels of renewable energy consumption.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Pakistan's Economic Indicators

	GDP	CO2	H_TE	HP	INVA	REC
Mean	3.033610	-0.372547	0.642217	-0.318011	3.005248	3.890342
Median	3.033667	-0.359857	0.654788	-0.271940	2.994790	3.870367
Maximum	3.162221	-0.084591	0.834079	0.111452	3.132486	4.062016
Minimum	2.935717	-0.681404	0.370261	-0.772190	2.864966	3.739810
Std. Dev.	0.069242	0.152550	0.082782	0.242094	0.082976	0.086503
Skewness	0.407081	-0.111553	-0.916005	-0.041800	-0.095491	0.192819
Kurtosis	1.918130	2.399951	6.238137	2.084583	1.787864	2.225775

Source: Author's estimate.

Before estimating the parameter coefficients, leverage plots of the regressors are examined to select the appropriate functional specification of the regression model. Some variables, such as CO2, INVA, HTE, and REC, exhibit potential outliers. Influential statistics are employed to address these outliers, ensuring the regression analysis's robustness and accuracy (see, Figure 1). These statistical procedures are crucial for conducting a comprehensive and reliable investigation into the relationships between the variables.

Figure 1: Leverage Plots

Source: Author's estimate.

Further, Figure 2 displays influence statistics to detect outliers and threshold points in the dataset. The RStudent Test identified two outliers, while the Hat Matrix Test indicated one threshold point. The DFFITS Test revealed two outliers, and the COVRATIO Test detected six threshold points. These statistics are vital for assessing the regression model's robustness and reliability. Identifying influential observations allows researchers to investigate data issues, understand their impact on results, and enhance the model's accuracy and generalizability. Careful examination of these points is essential for accurate interpretation and reliable conclusions from the regression analysis.

Figure 2: Influence Statistics

Source: Author's estimate.

After detecting potential outliers within the model, the study utilized the robust least squares MM-estimator, which effectively addresses outliers present in both the dependent and explanatory variables. The resulting estimate is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Robust Least Squares Regression: MM-estimator

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
CO2	0.411308	0.118444	3.472591	0.0005
H_TE	-0.029822	0.026960	-1.106146	0.2687
HP	0.257132	0.033103	7.767681	0.0000
INVA	0.065902	0.033778	1.951053	0.0511
REC	0.572284	0.242447	2.360452	0.0183
C	0.858733	0.877507	0.978605	0.3278
Robust Statistics				
R-squared	0.751113	Adjusted R-squared	0.701335	
Rw-squared	0.980766	Adjust Rw-squared	0.980766	
Akaike info criterion	49.49880	Schwarz criterion	62.72576	
Deviance	0.004520	Scale	0.010358	
Rn-squared statistic	1047.610	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)	0.000000	
Non-robust Statistics				
Mean dependent var	3.033610	S.D. dependent var	0.069242	
S.E. of regression	0.018534	Sum squared resid	0.008588	

Source: Author's estimate.

The findings reveal a significant positive correlation between CO₂ emissions and economic growth, proving that emissions play a crucial role in the country's growth trajectory. Economic growth and industrialization lead to increased energy consumption from fossil fuels, resulting in higher CO₂ emissions (Yusuf et al., 2023). Governments play a key role in decoupling economic growth from carbon emissions through policies like carbon pricing and renewable energy incentives (Liu et al., 2023). The relationship between GDP and CO₂ emissions varies among countries, and global efforts are focused on transitioning to sustainable, low-carbon economies to address climate change (Hassan et al., 2023). The industrial revolution has significantly contributed to rising CO₂ emissions due to fuel burning, deforestation, cement use, transportation, and manufacturing (Nunes, 2023). High technology adoption is vital for developing countries seeking economic participation, fostering knowledge transfer and potentially boosting high-tech industries' share in GDP and exports (Dao & Khuc, 2023). The relationship between international trade, intellectual property rights (IPRs), and FDI plays a crucial role in a country's innovation and economic growth. International trade benefits economic growth, introducing competition, efficiency, and improved capital inputs (Khan, 2023b). The coefficient for the number of physicians indicates a positive impact on economic growth, with each 1 unit increase in physicians associated with a 0.257 unit increase in GDP. Physicians contribute to healthcare quality, promoting population health and productivity and positively impacting economic growth (Siziba & Barnard, 2023). A 1 unit increase in renewable energy consumption is linked to a 0.572 unit increase in GDP, confirming the positive link between clean energy and economic growth, promoting well-being and mitigating environmental impacts. Using renewable energy improves environmental and economic performance, positively affecting public health and growth (Jie et al., 2023). Balancing economic and environmental actions is crucial, ensuring optimal renewable energy consumption to avoid negative effects on other socio-economic factors. In conclusion, Governments are responsible for shaping the relationship between economic growth and environmental sustainability through policy measures (Dzwigol et al., 2023; Tanweer et al., 2023). The findings emphasize the importance of transitioning towards sustainable practices and technologies to promote economic growth while safeguarding the environment and public health.

Figure 3 shows the CUSUM test at the 5% confidence level, which shows the model is stable and well-fitted over time, with no significant departures or structural changes in the relationship between variables.

Figure 3: CUSUM Test Estimates

Source: Author's estimate.

The Granger causality estimates provide significant insights into the relationships between the variables (see Table 3). The findings confirm growth-led emissions and increasing demand for renewable energy. High-tech exports play a causal role in stimulating economic growth, while economic growth contributes to health infrastructure development. Conversely, the quality of health infrastructure influences emissions and renewable energy demand.

Table 3: Granger Causality Estimates

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
CO2 does not Granger Cause GDP	29	0.07998	0.9234
GDP does not Granger Cause CO2		8.36243	0.0018
H_TE does not Granger Cause GDP	29	3.61518	0.0424
GDP does not Granger Cause H TE		0.31529	0.7326
HP does not Granger Cause GDP	29	2.01694	0.1550
GDP does not Granger Cause HP		3.06124	0.0654
INVA does not Granger Cause HP	29	0.74610	0.4849
HP does not Granger Cause INVA		0.57865	0.5683
REC does not Granger Cause HP	29	0.06345	0.9387
HP does not Granger Cause REC		5.02437	0.0150
INVA does not Granger Cause GDP	29	0.83175	0.4474
GDP does not Granger Cause INVA		0.22664	0.7989
REC does not Granger Cause GDP	29	0.04473	0.9563
GDP does not Granger Cause REC		4.05508	0.0304
H TE does not Granger Cause CO2	29	1.98692	0.1590
CO2 does not Granger Cause H_TE		0.57545	0.5700
HP does not Granger Cause CO2	29	4.63056	0.0199
CO2 does not Granger Cause HP		0.81494	0.4545
INVA does not Granger Cause CO2	29	0.33637	0.7177
CO2 does not Granger Cause INVA		0.31733	0.7311

Source: Author's estimate.

A well-developed health infrastructure can reduce emissions and promote investments in sustainable energy initiatives. Overall, these results highlight the interconnected dynamics between economic development, environmental sustainability, and public health within a country.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research sheds light on Pakistan's economic growth and interconnected factors from 1990 to 2020. It highlights the positive link between carbon emissions and economic growth, calling for sustainable policies. Health infrastructure, industrialization, and renewable energy demand positively impact economic growth, emphasizing healthcare and clean energy investments. The Granger causality test supports growth-led emissions, urging environmentally responsible strategies. Policy recommendations include carbon emission reduction, renewable energy projects, and enhancing health infrastructure. Promoting high-tech industries is essential for economic expansion. The study has limitations, including secondary data use and a limited time frame. Future research should include primary data and recent years for a comprehensive view. Longitudinal analyses and case studies can enrich our understanding, along with qualitative research and comparative studies with other countries. This research contributes to Pakistan's sustainable economic growth by balancing progress with the environment and public welfare, aided by policy measures and addressing research limitations.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

The data is freely available at World Development Indicators published by World Bank (2022) at <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>.

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